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Characterization of protonated and sulfonated vermiculite nanofillers for hybrid polymer membranes

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Abstract. Protonated and sulfonated clay minerals are promising nanofillers for hybrid nanocomposite membranes in order to increase their conductivity. The natural clay mineral vermiculite (VER) was protonated using sulfuric acid at varying concentrations of 0.1 M, 0.5 M, and 2 M. Based on XRD and FTIR analyses, the sample treated with 0.5M concentrated acid was selected as suitable material for further sulfonation, which was grafted by a two-step method performed by (3-mercaptopropyl)trimethoxysilane (3-MPTMS) followed by oxidation with H₂O₂. Structure and morphology of prepared samples was investigated by XRD, FTIR and SEM with EDAX analysis confirming successful attachment of sulfonic acid (-SO₃H) groups to the vermiculite structure.

1. Introduction

Membrane technologies using polymer membranes are an ideal choice for hydrogen production and purification due to their advantages such as operational versatility, high energy efficiency, compactness, environmental friendliness, low operating costs and energy efficiency.

A significant group in this field are proton exchange membranes (PEMs), where these polymers have sulfonic acid groups in their structure directly attached to their main chains. Despite their functional advantages, these membranes often suffer from undesirable phase separation between hydrophilic and hydrophobic domains, a consequence of their inherently rigid polymer backbones. Enhancing the degree of sulfonation can improve conductivity; however, it frequently compromises the membrane's mechanical integrity and chemical stability [1-3].

A great option are hybrid nanocomposite membranes, where clay minerals act as nanofillers in polymers. These clay-based nanofillers affect not only the membrane's physicochemical properties and separation performance such as permselectivity, ion flux, and conductivity, but also enhance its mechanical and thermal stability. They themselves reduce the ionic conductivity and ion exchange capacity of the membranes due to their inactive ionic groups. To improve the ionic conductivity and ion exchange capacity of the membranes, the structure/surface of these

clay minerals can be activated with acids, namely by protonation or by sulfonic acid group ($-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$) [4-6].

Vermiculite is clay mineral that, compared to more widely used smectites, especially montmorillonite, possesses a higher layer charge resulting primarily from tetrahedral substitution. The magnitude of layer charge on the vermiculite layers has a key effect on the amount of intercalated/anchored organic molecules and on their arrangement [7].

While the acidification of the clay mineral vermiculite has been described in several works in the past [8-10], relatively few publications address its sulfonation [11,12], and those that do often lack a detailed analysis of the resulting material structures.

In this study, nanofillers based on the clay mineral vermiculite were synthesized and characterized. The vermiculite was first protonated using sulfuric acid at varying concentrations, followed by a sulfonation process. The main goal was to investigate the influence of acid concentration on the structure of the prepared samples during the protonation of vermiculite, in order to identify the most suitable sample for subsequent sulfonation. The successful attachment of sulfonic acid ($-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$) groups to the vermiculite structure was then confirmed. The resulting materials exhibit significant potential for application as nanofillers in hybrid polymer membranes.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

The natural clay mineral vermiculite (abbreviated VER) from a deposit in Brazil (supplied by Grena Co., Veselí nad Lužnicí, Czech Republic) was milled, sieved, and the fraction below 40 μm was used for experiments. Its crystallochemical formula calculated from the results of the elemental analysis was $(\text{Si}_{6.16}\text{Al}_{1.84})(\text{Al}_{0.08}\text{Fe}^{3+}_{0.72}\text{Fe}^{2+}_{0.04}\text{Mg}_{4.88}\text{Ti}_{0.12})\text{O}_{20}(\text{OH})_4(\text{Ca}_{0.30}\text{K}_{0.36}\text{Na}_{0.16})$ and the cation exchange capacity (CEC) was 106 $\text{cmol}(+)/\text{kg}$. Other chemicals for clay acidification were sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4 , w = 98%, Mach Chemikálie Co.), hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2 , w = 30%, Mach Chemikálie Co.), toluene (p.a., Mach Chemikálie Co.) and (3-mercaptopropyl)trimethoxysilane (3-MPTMS, w = 95%, SigmaAldrich).

2.2 Preparation of protonated vermiculite nanofillers

To protonate vermiculite (VER), sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) stock solutions of 0.1 M, 0.5 M, and 2 M concentrations were prepared. For each treatment, 120 mL of the respective H_2SO_4 solution was combined with 12 g of VER, and the mixture was stirred continuously at 80 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 4 hours. The resulting suspension was washed repeatedly with deionized water until a neutral pH was achieved. Excess water was removed by centrifugation. Depending on the acid concentration, washing and centrifugation steps were repeated 3 to 6 times. The resulting solid was then dried overnight at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$. The final products were labelled accordingly: H_VER_01M, H_VER_05M and H_VER_2M.

2.3 Preparation of sulfonated vermiculite nanofiller

Based on prior analyses, the H_VER_0.5M sample was selected as the starting material for sulfonation. A total of 5 g of H_VER_0.5M was mixed with 50 mL of 3-mercaptopropyltrimethoxysilane (3-MPTMS) and 100 mL of toluene. The resulting mixture was placed in a flask, which was then immersed in an oil bath and refluxed at 180 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 hours under continuous stirring.

The anchored –SH groups on the vermiculite surface were oxidized using a 10% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) solution, with stirring continued overnight. To complete the oxidation process, the material was further treated with a 0.1 M H₂SO₄ solution, stirred for 4 hours. The product was then washed thoroughly with deionized water and centrifuged repeatedly until a neutral pH was achieved. Finally, the sulfonated vermiculite (VER_SO3H) was dried overnight at 60 °C.

2.4 Characterization

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were measured using the X-ray diffractometer Rigaku Ultima IV (Rigaku, Japan, CuK α radiation, NiK β filter, scintillation detector, Bragg-Brentano arrangement) in ambient atmosphere under constant conditions (40 kV, 40 mA, scanning range 2-60° 2 θ , scanning speed 3.5°/min).

The FTIR spectra of all samples were measured by ATR (Attenuated Total Reflectance) technique on a single-reflection diamond ATR crystal. The FTIR spectra were collected using FT-IR spectrometer Nicolet iS50 (ThermoScientific, USA) with DTGS detector. The measurement parameters were the following: spectral region 4000-400 cm⁻¹, spectral resolution 4 cm⁻¹; 64 scans; Happ-Genzel apodization.

The nanofillers morphology was investigated using scanning transmission electron microscope (JEOL JSM-7610F, France). The samples were attached to the metal targets and coated with a gold thin film. An accelerating voltage of 15 kV and a secondary electron detector (SEI) were used in the measurement.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 XRD diffraction

The XRD pattern of natural VER (Fig. 1) correspond to Mg-vermiculites with characteristic reflection with the interlayer distances $d = 1.429$ nm corresponding to two layers of water molecules in the interlayer. The second reflection with $d = 1.236$ nm with lower content of water molecules [13,14].

Acidification of natural VER with 0.1 M or 0.5 M H₂SO₄ stock solutions caused small shifts of VER reflections on values $d = 1.432$ nm and 1.258 nm for H_VER_01M and $d = 1.375$ nm and 1.201 nm for H_VER_05M. However, the significant reduction in intensities was observed (Fig. 1) for these two samples. On the other hand, the acid treatment of natural VER with the strongest 2M H₂SO₄ solution caused the major dissolution and total collapse of the vermiculite structure [15,16] as observed by the disappearance of both main VER reflections for sample H_VER_2M.

The reflection with the interlayer distance $d = 1.375$ nm disappeared in XRD pattern (Fig. 1) for sulfonated sample VER_SO3H due to the sulfonation of VER structure and its partial amorphization. The similar results were obtained in the work Moraes et al. [11].

Figure 1. XRD patterns of natural VER, its protonated forms H_VER_01M, H_VER_05M, H_VER_2M and sulfonated VER_SO3H.

3.2 FTIR analysis

The FTIR spectrum of the natural VER (Fig. 3) shows a band at 3363 cm^{-1} in the O-H stretching region attributed to structural OH groups and vibration at 1644 cm^{-1} corresponded to the OH bending vibration of adsorbed water. The intensive band at 952 cm^{-1} is assigned to Si-O stretching vibrations. The weak bands at 730 cm^{-1} and 660 cm^{-1} and are related to in-plane deformation vibrations of Al-O-Si bonds of VER [17].

Spectral changes after acidification of VER at lower concentrations of the acid used affect mainly the peak intensities. Interlayer cations are gradually washed out of the structure and acid ions bind to the clay structure, and therefore the acid mainly affects the peak intensity of the valence and deformation bonds of OH and Si-O, whose intensities decreases.

While under the strongest acid treatment ($2\text{M H}_2\text{SO}_4$) there are also more significant shifts in the FTIR spectrum of H_VER_2M. The appearance of the new band at 1054 cm^{-1} belongs to the stretching vibration of Si-O bonds of amorphous silica, which forms in the acid treated clay minerals [8, 18]. These findings are in agreement with XRD results.

Figure 2. The FTIR spectra of natural VER and its protonated forms H_VER_01M, H_VER_05M, H_VER_2M.

The Fig. 3 compares FTIR spectra of natural VER, protonated H_VER_05M a sulfonated VER_SO3H prepared from it. The spectrum of VER_SO3H shows new band at 1041 cm^{-1} attributed to symmetric stretching vibration $\nu_s(\text{O}=\text{S}=\text{O})$ of SO_3H group [19,20] anchoring on clay surface, while the original peak belonging to Si-O stretching vibrations (950 cm^{-1}) now shows only weak intensity. These findings confirmed successful sulfonation of VER.

Figure 3. The FTIR spectra of natural VER, protonated H_VER_05M and sulfonated VER_SO3H.

3.3 Morphology of vermiculite nanofillers

The surface morphology of vermiculite nanofillers was studied using SEM (Fig. 4a) and SEM-EDS mapping (Fig. 4b) was used to analyze the elemental changes in the concentrations of magnesium (Mg), potassium (K) and sulfur (S) elements - Fig. 4c).

The natural vermiculite particles (VER) were oval shaped with rounded edges. Surface deformation of the upper layer was visible on the particles. This was caused by the ball milling process which was used to prepare the under-screen fraction <math><40\ \mu\text{m}</math>. VER particles after acid treatment show a smooth surface. The proportion of very fine particles with sharp edges has increased (see the SEM image detail, H_VER_05M). SEM-EDS mapping was used to analyse the distribution of interlayer cations, especially the Mg and K elements (Fig. 4c). It was found that acid treatment decreased their concentration.

The sulfonation of H_VER_05M nanofillers had no significant effect on the structural and morphological changes (VER_SO3H). However, it did cause the particle surfaces to become smoother and slightly wrinkled. Defects in the form of round holes were found very sporadically on the particle surface. SEM-EDS mapping confirmed the presence of sulphur (S) mainly on the edges of the particles; on the other hand the potassium was not detected. The occurrence and concentration of magnesium (Mg) is similar that in the original VER particles.

Figure 4. The SEM images of natural VER, protonated H_VER_05M and sulfonated VER_SO3H samples (a), EDS mapping (b). Detail of the elemental distributions (c) of Mg (green colour), K (brown colour) and S (violet colour) on the surface samples.

4. Conclusion

The objective of this study was to functionalize the clay mineral vermiculite with sulfonic acid groups incorporated into its structure. Since acidification of the surface of the clay mineral using sulfuric acid is essential for sulfonation, the influence of the concentration of this acid on the resulting structure was evaluated through X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). The results indicated that an acid concentration of 0.5 M is optimal for further modification, as higher concentrations, specifically 2 M lead to the complete collapse of the vermiculite structure.

The sulfonic acid group containing clay mineral vermiculite was prepared using the ion exchange method with silicate compound 3-MPTMS. Techniques as XRD, FTIR and SEM with EDAX confirmed successful attachment of sulfonic acid ($-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$) groups to the vermiculite structure.

These materials are suitable candidates as nanofillers for hybrid nanocomposite membranes to increase their proton conductivity.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in repository ZENODO at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15690165>.

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